

Institute of Discourse Perspective

2nd International Conference

Syed Maududi's Thought: Dynamics & Impact

The phenomenal speaker presents this research in 2nd International Conference Syed Maududi's Thought: Dynamics &, held on 25-27 April 2025 at Al-Razi Hall, University of the Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan. The Conference Abstract is published on behalf of the decision of acceptance and approval of aforesaid Conference Organizing Committee.

Correspondence:

Hafiz Sajid Iqbal PhD, Chair of Organizing Committee, 2nd International Conference, Institute of discourse Perspectives, E.:
conferences.idp@gmail.com |
www.idpinstitute.com | +92 300 496 9385
| +92 333 4060783

Conference Secretariat: Fayaz Khan Jadoon, Institute of Islamic Perspective and Guidance, University of Management and Technology C-II, Johar Town, Lahore Pakistan. T.: +92 42 35212801-10, <https://www.umat.edu.pk>

Citation:

Muhammad Muhsin, 2nd International Conference, Syed Maududi's Thought: Dynamics &, held in Al-Razi Hall, University of the Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan. Vol. 12 (2025).
p. 9-10.

Competing Interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Additional information is available at the end of the article.

Conference Abstract

SYED ABUL A'LA MAUDUDI'S CONCEPT OF THE ISLAMIC SYSTEM OF LIFE: A COMPREHENSIVE FRAMEWORK FOR PRESENT SOCIETY

Muhammad Muhsin

MPhil Scholar of Islamic Thought and Civilization at University of Management and Technology, Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan

Ethics approval and consent to participate: No ethical approval needed for this research work.

Consent for publication: Author is agreed to submit this abstract for publication in this research journal.

Availability of data and materials: The information and data collected and/ or incorporated in this study is included in this manuscript.

ABSTRACT

Syed Abul A'la Maududi (1903–1979), a renowned Islamic thinker and founder of Jamaat-e-Islami, developed a comprehensive framework for the Islamic system of life. His ideology integrates spiritual, political, economic, and social aspects under the sovereignty of Allah, emphasizing the implementation of Shariah as the guiding principle for governance and daily life. Maududi's vision advocates for an Islamic state governed by divine laws, rejecting secularism and materialistic ideologies. He presents Islam as a complete code of life, where faith is not limited to personal worship but extends to societal structures, ensuring justice, morality, and equity. This paper explores Maududi's key ideas on Islamic governance, economic principles, and social justice, highlighting their relevance in contemporary Muslim societies. His contributions continue to shape modern Islamic movements and discourses on the role of Islam in politics and governance.

Keywords: *Islamic System, Modern approach, Comprehensiveness, Complete code of life.*

© 2025The Author(s). This open access article is distributed under a Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY) 4.0 license.

You are free to:

Share — copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format

Adapt — remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially.

The licensor cannot revoke these freedoms as long as you follow the license terms.

Under the following terms:

Attribution — You must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made.

You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use.

No additional restrictions

You may not apply legal terms or technological measures that legally restrict others from doing anything the license permits